

COMPARISON OF AGGRESSION AND COMPETITION ANXIETY BETWEEN THE FINALISTS OF ALL INDIA INTER UNIVERSITY BALL BADMINTON MEN TOURNAMENT

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Introduction:

Sports psychology is a specialized field within psychology that focuses on understanding and improving the mental and emotional aspects of athletic performance. Sports psychologists work with athletes, coaches, and teams to enhance performance, motivation, and overall well-being. Aggression and anxiety are two common psychological factors that can significantly impact athletes in sports. Aggression in sports can stem from a competitive drive to win, which is essential for peak performance. Controlled aggression can motivate athletes to push their limits and perform at their best. Being assertive on the field can help athletes stand their ground and make effective plays. Uncontrolled aggression can lead to hostility, resulting in conflicts with opponents, teammates, and officials. In extreme cases, uncontrolled aggression can escalate to violence, resulting in injuries and disciplinary actions. Athletes can benefit from anger management techniques to control their emotions and reactions. Physical symptoms like increased heart rate, butterflies in the stomach, or tension. Anxiety often arises from the fear of not meeting personal or others' expectations. Athletes may feel anxious due to the pressure to perform well, especially in high-stakes situations. Anxiety can result from the fear of judgment from coaches, peers, or spectators. Thorough physical and mental preparation through practice and mental rehearsal can boost confidence and reduce anxiety..

Methodology:

The purpose of the study was to compare the aggression and competition anxiety between Finalists of [Winners and Runner-Up in All India Inter University Men Ball Badminton Tournament] in All India Inter University Ball Badminton Men Tournament. To achieve this purpose of the study, twenty men Ball Badminton players representing SRM Institute of Science & Technology and BS Abdur Rahman Crescent Institute of Science & Technology [Finalists] were selected as subjects at random. Among the psychological variables, the following variables namely aggression and competition anxiety were selected as criterion variables. All the subjects of two groups were tested on selected dependent variables by using standard tests. The independent ‘t’ ratio was used to analyze the significant difference, if any between groups. The .05 level of confidence was fixed as the level of significance to test the ‘t’ ratio obtained, which was considered as an appropriate.

Analysis of the Data:

Aggression:

The mean, standard deviation and ‘t’ ratio values on aggression of Winners and Runner-Up in All India Inter University Men Ball Badminton Tournament have been analyzed and presented in Table 1.

Table 1: The Mean, Standard Deviation and ‘t’ Ratio Values between Winners and Runner-Up in all India Inter University Men Ball Badminton Tournament on Aggression

Groups	Mean	Standard Deviation	‘t’ Ratio Value
Winners	24.33	0.87	0.55
Runner-Up	24.11	0.91	

* Significant at .05 level of confidence.

(The table values required for significance at .05 level of confidence with df 18 was 1.73).

The table 1 shows that the mean values on aggression for Winners and Runner-Up in All India Inter University Men Ball Badminton Tournament were 24.33 and 24.11 respectively. The obtained ‘t’ ratio value on aggression 0.55 which was lesser than the table value required for significance with df 18 was 1.73. The results of the study showed that there was no significant difference between university men Winners and Runner-Up in All India Inter University Men Ball Badminton Tournament on aggression.

Competition Anxiety:

The mean, standard deviation and ‘t’ ratio values on competition anxiety of Winners and Runner-Up in All India Inter University Men Ball Badminton Tournament have been analyzed and presented in table 2.

Table 2: The Mean, Standard Deviation and 't' Ratio Values Between Winners and Runner-Up in All India Inter University Men Ball Badminton Tournament on Competition Anxiety

Groups	Mean	Standard Deviation	't' Ratio Value
Winners	16.74	1.17	0.29
Runner-Up	16.59	1.16	

* Significant at .05 level of confidence.

(The table values required for significance at .05 level of confidence with df 18 was 1.73).

The table 2 shows that the mean values on competition anxiety for Winners and Runner-Up in All India Inter University Men Ball Badminton Tournament were 16.74 and 16.59 respectively. The obtained 't' ratio value on competition anxiety 0.29 which was lesser than the table value required for significance with df 18 was 1.73. The results of the study showed that there was no significant difference between university men Winners and Runner-Up in All India Inter University Men Ball Badminton Tournament on competition anxiety.

Conclusions:

- There was no significant difference between Winners and Runner-Up in All India Inter University Men Ball Badminton Tournament on aggression.
- There was no significant difference between Winners and Runner-Up in All India Inter University Men Ball Badminton Tournament on competition anxiety.

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